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The Role of Local Heroes in Patriotic Education of Youth

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***Abstract:** This article pays special attention to the role of local heroes in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism. The purpose of the article is to inculcate in the consciousness of the young generation the bravery and heroism of our Jizzakh ancestors in the fight against fascism in the Second World War, along with our ancestors like Tomaris, Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi and Amir Temur, who fought for the freedom and independence of our country.*

***Key words:** Patriotism, the era of globalization, the second world war, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Uzbek heroes, Jorakul Torayev, Dubrova village, Jorakhan Usmanov, Eshankul Ismailov, Tugonboy Koumboyev, Avazmat Niyazmatov..*

INTRODUCTION

In the Second World War, which brought the greatest disaster and casualties to mankind, brave children of the Uzbek people fought valiantly against the scourge of fascism, among all the peace-loving peoples of the world. In recent years, the scientific study of the contribution of Uzbeks to the victory in the Second World War, their heroism and hard work at the front and behind the front is becoming one of the urgent tasks for historians and scientists.

Nowadays, in Uzbekistan, it is important to educate young people in the spirit of national ideals and loyalty to the Motherland, that the protection of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty, the patriotism and heroism shown by our compatriots who sacrificed their lives for the freedom and independence of the Motherland, their loyalty, dedication, fortitude and courage promoting such qualities is one of the main tasks.

MAIN PART

In this place, along with our ancestors like Tomaris, Shiroq, Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, who fought for the independence and freedom of our country, inculcate in the consciousness of the young generation the bravery and heroism of our ancestors in the battles against fascism in the Second World War. is appropriate. [1].

In the Second World War, along with all nations, the brave sons of the Uzbek people fought valiantly against fascism. In recent years, not enough attention has been paid to studying the bravery and heroism of Uzbek soldiers in the Second World War and covering them in the media. In this regard, our honorable president Sh.M. Mirziyoyev expressed the following thoughts in his speech dedicated to the "Remembrance and Appreciation" day on May 9, 2018. "Using today's opportunity, I would like to make a proposal to our historical scholars, literary and artistic figures, and our general public. I think it's time to create new works about the heroism of our ancestors who participated in this terrible war, including preparing and publishing a perfect book-album based on accurate historical documents" [2].

The multinational people of Uzbekistan also showed true courage and selflessness and made a great contribution to the victory over fascism. In particular, about 2 million of our compatriots participated in the battles, more than 500,000 of them died heroically, and more than 60,000 of our compatriots returned from the war disabled. More than 120,000 war participants from Uzbekistan were awarded orders and medals. 301 of them were awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union. [3]

At the same time, during the war, our republic became one of the important supply centers for supplying food, clothing, weapons and other means necessary for the front. In particular, our compatriots took in their arms more than 1.5 million elderly people, women and young children who were relocated to Uzbekistan from the regions where the fighting is going on, and showed them incomparable care in difficult times.

In this article, the bravery and bravery of several Heroes of the Soviet Union from Jizzakh who were awarded such a high title, as well as the heroism of Jizzakh fighters in the Brest Fortress in the first days of the war, are covered based on information from archives and military literature. One of them is Hero of the Soviet Union Dzhorakul Torayev.

Zhorakul Torayev was born on March 20, 1922 in the village of Kaliya Molkanlik, Jizzakh District (now Sharaf Rashidov District), Jizzakh Region. In 1941, he was drafted into the ranks of the Soviet Army. Since 1941, he participated in battles on various fronts, including the Bryansk, Central and Belarusian fronts, and was seriously wounded twice.

From December 1943, junior sergeant Jorakul Torayev participated in military battles as a marksman in the 1007th light artillery regiment of the 12th artillery division of the 46th light artillery brigade of the 65th army of the Belorussian front.

On December 21, 1943, the 2nd battery, in which junior sergeant Zhorakul Torayev served, was assigned the task of protecting the strategically important hill number 143.3 near the village of Dubrova, Svetlogorsk district, Gomel region of the present Republic of Belarus, from enemy attack. . In the defense of the hill, the bravery of the marksman Jo'rakul Torayev, who heroically entered the battle against 27 enemy tanks and thousands of infantrymen, played an important role. In this battle, junior sergeant Jorakul Torayev knocked out 5 enemy tanks. Dzhorakul Torayev, who was seriously wounded and concussed, did not leave the battlefield and continued to fire against enemy tanks. Even though he was wounded, he brought a shell and shot the cannon and knocked out the enemy's fifth tank. After that, as a result of a strong explosion, he lost consciousness. 143.3 hills were saved thanks to the heroism of Jorakul Torayev and the soldiers of the 2nd battery, who regained consciousness in the field medical battalion.[4]

Before this battle, 12 enemy tanks, 2 "Ferdinand" heavy self-propelled guns and a number of infantrymen were destroyed by Sergeant Jorakul Torayev. Junior Sergeant Jorakul Torayev was

awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union and the Order of the Golden Star by the decision of the Presidium of the Family Soviet of the USSR dated March 29, 1944 for his heroism in this battle.

On May 7, 2017, a memorial monument was erected in his honor on the hill near the village of Dubrova, Svetlogorsk region, Gomel region, Gomel region, Republic of Belarus, where Dzhorakul Torayev was a hero. [5]

Another hero of the Second World War, a soldier of the 1st Belorussian Front, 240th Rifle Regiment of the 8th Army, Eshankul Ismailov from Gallaorol, who is remembered with great pride. Eshankul Ismailov was born on March 1, 1902 in the village of Turk, Gallaorol district, Jizzakh region.

He was called up for military service in 1942, and from 1943 he fought on the 3rd Ukrainian and 1st Belarussian fronts. In the battles for the Dnieper, Odessa and Belarus took part in offensive operations. In January 1945, E. Ismailov showed exceptional heroism and example in the battles to capture the city-fortress of Poznan. E. Ismailov destroyed several enemy checkpoints and about 40 enemy soldiers in the battle. Inspired by the heroism of E. Ismailov, the battalion attacked and the enemy hospital was captured with about 400 wounded soldiers.[6]

In the subsequent battles for Poznan, E. Ismailov killed about 20 enemies. On January 29, 1945, severely wounded E. Ismailov did not leave the battlefield and continued the battle.

According to the decision of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR on May 31, 1945, Eshankul Ismailov was awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union and the "Golden Star" medal. [7]

Another one of the heroes of this glorious past is Jorakhan Usmanov. Jorakhan Usmanov was born on February 12, 1922 in the village of Savat, Yangiabad District, Jizzakh Region, in a peasant family. He was drafted into the ranks of the Red Army in 1942, and from March he participated in the battles against the enemy in the ranks of the active army [8].

On September 29, 1943, senior sergeant Jorakhan Usmanov, the assistant platoon commander of the 237th Rifle Regiment, showed heroism when crossing the Soj River near the village of Karpovka, Gomel region of the present Republic of Belarus. Senior sergeant Jorakhan Usmanov, who was one of the first to cross the river, repelled 13 enemy counterattacks with his 8 surviving comrades and ensured the passage of the main forces of the Red Army. Jorakhan Usmanov was seriously wounded in this battle [9].

By the decision of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR on January 15, 1944, senior sergeant Dzhorakhon Usmanov was awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union and the "Golden Star" medal for his personal bravery in the fight against the German-Nazi invaders and exemplary performance of the assigned military mission [10].

Another war hero, Togonboy Koumboev, was born on March 20, 1922, in the village of Chimkurgon, Farish district, Jizzakh region, in a peasant family.

He was sent to the Red Army in January 1942 by the military conscription department of Farish district. As a result of his bravery and bravery in battles, Koumboev Togonboy was appointed the commander of the 20th special reconnaissance company of the Sevsk Rifle Division of the 65th Army of the Central Front.

In 1943, when the Soviet troops crossed the Dnieper River, Sergeant Koumboev Togonboy and his 20th special reconnaissance company were given a special task. According to the assignment, the 20th special reconnaissance company led by Sergeant Koumboev Togonboy crossed the Dnieper River

and occupied the town of Loyev, located in the Gomel region of the present Republic of Belarus, and it was ensured that the paratroopers of the Red Army landed on the right bank of the Dnieper.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Pursuant to the Resolution of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR dated October 30, 1943, Sergeant Koumbojev Togonboy was awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union along with Lenin for his bravery in the battles against the German-fascist invaders, in particular, for his heroism during the crossing of the Dnieper River by Soviet troops. was awarded with the Order and "Golden Star" medal. [11]

Another war hero is Avazmat Niyozmatov. He was born in 1922 in the village of Yom, Zomin district, and was involved in horse sports before he was drafted into the army. At that time, there was a point for preparing horses for the Red Army in the collective farm of Y. Okhunboboyev of the Zomin district, and Avazmat Asov used to tame the horses, and then the horses were sent to a special place.

Avazmat, who was called up for military service, served in the Brest fortress. On June 22, 1941, the Nazi invaders surrounded the fortress from all sides. A small garrison of Brest fortress under the leadership of R. Gavrilov, I. Zubachyov, Y. Fomin is defending. Avazmat Niyozmatov from Zamin was also in defense of the fortress along with several Uzbek soldiers.

When the castle was surrounded by the enemy, in addition to the soldiers, there were their families and young children inside the castle. Women and young children had to be taken out of the siege to safety. Relative weakness of the enemy was found at the eastern gate of the fortress. There was an enemy camp at the eastern gate, and private soldier Avazmat Niyozmatov was ordered to destroy the enemy camp. He was wounded while leaving the fortress through the Bug river. However, Avazmat fulfills the combat mission. Detonate the enemy's dzoti and die as a result of a powerful explosion. A brave Uzbek son sacrificed his life and ensured that many women and young children passed from the enemy's encirclement to a safe place in the forest.

This incident happened on the third day of the war, that is, in June, and it was the soldier Avazmat Niyozmatov from Zamin who blew up the enemy's first firing point in the war. [12]

In 1988, the name of Avazmat Niyozmatov was permanently inscribed on a marble stone in the Brest memorial complex. Information about his life and heroism is located in the 9th hall of the museum.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, as there are heroes of the nation in every era, during the Second World War, the Uzbeks who sacrificed their lives for the independence and peace of the Motherland and showed heroism, including Jizzakh's Jurakul Torayev, Jurakhon Usmanov, Ismail Eshonkulov, Togonboy Koumbojev, Avazmat Niyozmatov have grown up. Nowadays, it is important to promote and recognize among the youth the heroism of the veterans of the Second World War and the labor behind the front, which they showed on the front and behind the front, in the education of young people in the spirit of patriotism. Such activities will give a high result if they are carried out together with spiritual and educational activities in the neighborhood, schools and higher education institutions. The participation of participants of the Second World War and labor veterans behind the front in the events organized in this regard is especially important for educating students of higher educational institutions in the spirit of patriotism.

REFERENCE:

1. The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to increase the effectiveness of education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism". 29.06.2023
2. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. May 9 - Day of Remembrance and Appreciation. May 9, 2019.
3. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. About measures to prepare and hold the Day of Remembrance and Appreciation. Tashkent. 2021.
4. Names and feats. (Handbook). Main editorial board of the Uzbek Soviet Encyclopedia. Tashkent. 1990. p.262-263
5. A. Stepanova. Memory of the heart (On the 95th anniversary of the birth of the Hero of the Soviet Union Nikolai Spiridonovich Pavlov). Moscow., 2017. p.16-19
6. A. Stepanova. Memory of the heart (On the 95th anniversary of the birth of the Hero of the Soviet Union Nikolai Spiridonovich Pavlov). Moscow., 2017. p.22
7. Names and feats. (Handbook). Main editorial board of the Uzbek Soviet Encyclopedia. Tashkent. 1990. p.104
8. Heroes of the Soviet Union - Uzbeks. Tashkent. "Uzbekistan". 1984 p.125
9. H. Haydarov, Q. Usmanov. History of Jizzakh (Historical memory and records about the city of Jizzakh). Tashkent. "Teacher". 2009. p.147.
10. Heroes of the Soviet Union are Uzbek citizens. Tashkent. "Uzbekistan". 1984, p.327
11. Names and exploits. (Directory). Main editorial office of the Uzbek Soviet Encyclopedia. Tashkent. 1990. p.270-271
12. Names and exploits. (Directory). Main editorial office of the Uzbek Soviet Encyclopedia. Tashkent. p.120
13. Uzbekistan during the Second World War. "Uzbekistan", Tashkent. 2023. p.19-20